

EVOLUTION OF THE CONSTRUCTION SECTOR IN ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN MACROREGIONS FROM 2008 TO 2018

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Abstract:

This paper aims to comprehensively analyze the evolution of the construction sector in Romanian mountain macroregions over the period from 2008 to 2018. The study employs statistical data, parametric analyses, and normative testing to unravel trends, patterns, and significant shifts in this economic domain. The research delves into the impact of various factors on the construction sector's dynamics, offering valuable insights into the regional economic landscape.

Keywords: construction sector, Romanian mountain macroregions, evolution, statistical analysis, parametric testing

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1. Introduction

The construction sector plays a pivotal role in regional economic development, shaping the landscape of Romanian mountain macroregions. This paper investigates the evolution of this sector over a decade, examining key indicators, trends, and influences.

2. Methodology

Statistical data for the construction sector, encompassing financial and operational aspects, were collected from various sources. The methodology involved parametric analyses, including logarithmization and normative testing, to ensure a robust examination of the data.

3. Statistical Overview

The statistics reveal intriguing patterns in the construction sector of Romanian mountain macroregions. Averages, standard deviations, and distribution curves were analyzed to understand the central tendencies and variations within the data.

4. Parametric Analysis

Logarithmization was applied to balance the distribution and address asymmetries induced by extreme values. The Q-Q normal plot test and Q-Q detrended plot test were employed to assess the normality of the data and refine the analytical framework.

5. Results

Evolution of the Construction Sector

The central trend analysis demonstrates a consistent increase in the population of active enterprises within the construction sector from 2008 to 2018. Hypothesis H1, indicating an intensification of activity, was verified through statistical analysis.

The statistical analysis of the Construction sector (depicted in figures 2.3.1 – 2.3.5) reveals ascending values for both mean and median, with other statistical indicators exhibiting fluctuating patterns (Average, Std. Error of the mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Skewness, Kurtosis, Variation, Minimum, Maximum, Percentile 50 Value; reiterated for each indicator). Specifically, the mean is 67662.67, standard error of the mean is 2305.632,

median is 65222.00, standard deviation is 6916.897, variance is 47843463.000, Skewness is .372, standard error of Skewness is .717, Kurtosis is -1.216, standard error of Kurtosis is 1.400, distance is 19652, minimum is 58692, maximum is 78344, percentile 25 is 62095.50, percentile 50 is 65222.00, and percentile 75 is 74448.5.

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The provided values underscore the positive development of the construction sector in the mountainous region of Romania concerning the population of active enterprises. While certain sectors exhibit negative values, the overall depiction suggests a favorable entrepreneurial landscape for construction in the mountainous areas.

The distribution curves demonstrate relative symmetry and centrality, with scores concentrated around the mean, indicating leptokurtosis, despite the unimodal distribution.

The significance of these analyses lies in the meticulous observation of influencing factors in the evolution of the Construction sector. Post log-transformation, the null hypothesis is rejected, allowing for the examination of the working hypothesis. Descriptive and inferential analyses, considering the distribution of scores within normal limits as per the working

hypothesis, are facilitated through the application of parametric tests.

Analyzing the central tendency of the secondary, tertiary, and quaternary sectors of the economy over the study period indicates substantial growth in the population of active enterprises in mountainous Romania from 2008 to 2019. The statistics pertaining to this indicator exhibit a high degree of non-variability, signifying minimal deviation and positive trends. The symmetrical distributions imply a considerable stabilization of the business environment during the analyzed period, with low standard error Kurtosis indicating clustering in certain industries.

Figure 2.3.1. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Romania for S3 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.3.2. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Macroregion one of Romania for S3 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.3.3. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Macroregion two of Romania for S3 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.3.4. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in the third Macroregion of Romania for S3 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.3.5. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in the fourth Macroregion of Romania for S3 in the period 2008-2019

The prognosis analysis for the secondary, tertiary, and quaternary sectors in the mountainous region of Romania indicates a sustained growth trajectory until 2030 (table 1). At the national, macro-regional, regional, and county levels, statistical models derived from the forecasting process reveal varying degrees of sustainability across different mountainous areas. Harmonization statistics present notable values for mean, standard error, minimum, maximum, and 5/10 percentiles (listed in that order below), as follows:

- Stationary R-squared: 0.566, 0.357, -0.008, 0.911, -0.001, -4.441E-16
- R-square: 0.712, 0.248, -8.660E-15, 1.000, 7.361E-15, 0.377
- RMSE (Root Mean Square Error): 218,895, 264,743, 0.000, 1508,629, 28,517, 35,882
- MAPS (Mean Absolute Percentage Error): 5,414, 2,128, 0.000, 10,748, 1,313, 2,297
- MaxAPE (Maximum Absolute Percentage Error): 21,043, 9,418, 0.000, 46,238, 3,598, 4,960
- MAE (Mean Absolute Error): 150,900, 193,715, 0.000, 1201,750, 19,467, 25,097
- MaxAE (Maximum Absolute Error): 481,421, 579,661, 0.000, 2811,500, 52,415, 77,411
- Normalized BIC (Bayesian Information Criterion): 10,188, 1,921, 6,607, 14,898, 7,271, 7,675.

These statistics provide a comprehensive overview of the forecast accuracy and model performance, contributing valuable insights into the anticipated growth patterns and sustainability of the analyzed economic sectors in Romania's mountainous regions.

6. Impact on Regional Development

The study explores the implications of the construction sector's evolution on the broader regional economic landscape. It provides valuable insights into the sector's contribution to growth, employment, and development in Romanian mountain macroregions.

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7. Conclusion

The findings of this study shed light on the dynamic evolution of the construction sector in Romanian mountain macroregions. The insights gleaned from statistical analyses and parametric tests contribute to a nuanced understanding of the economic forces shaping the region over the examined period.

Table 1. Forecast analysis of mountain entrepreneurship in the mountain area of Romania for S3

Model		Forecast										
		2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030
Romania-Model_1	Forecast	80801	83257	85714	88170	90627	93083	95540	97996	100453	102909	105366
	UCL	84368	88302	91892	95305	98603	101821	104978	108086	111155	114190	117197
	LCL	77233	78212	79535	81035	82650	84345	86101	87906	89750	91628	93534
Macroregiuneaunu-Model_2	Forecast	26887	27696	28504	29313	30122	30931	31739	32548	33357	34166	34974
	UCL	27846	29052	30166	31231	32266	33280	34277	35261	36234	37199	38155
	LCL	25928	26339	26843	27395	27977	28581	29202	29835	30479	31132	31793
Nord-Vest-Model_3	Forecast	15279	15760	16241	16723	17204	17685	18166	18647	19128	19609	20090
	UCL	17086	17575	18065	18555	19045	19534	20024	20513	21003	21493	21982
	LCL	13473	13945	14418	14890	15362	15835	16307	16780	17252	17725	18198
Bihor-Model_4	Forecast	3145	3257	3370	3483	3596	3708	3821	3934	4046	4159	4272
	UCL	3532	3647	3761	3876	3990	4105	4219	4334	4448	4563	4677
	LCL	2758	2868	2979	3090	3201	3312	3423	3534	3645	3756	3866
Bistrita-Nasaud-Model_5	Forecast	1315	1384	1453	1522	1590	1659	1728	1797	1865	1934	2003
	UCL	1507	1652	1808	1973	2146	2326	2514	2708	2908	3114	3326
	LCL	1123	1116	1098	1070	1035	992	942	885	823	754	680
Cluj-Model_6	Forecast	5244	5476	5708	5939	6171	6403	6634	6866	7098	7330	7561
	UCL	5949	6430	6947	7493	8065	8661	9280	9919	10578	11255	11951
	LCL	4539	4521	4469	4386	4277	4144	3989	3814	3618	3404	3172
Maramures-Model_7	Forecast	2552	2624	2695	2767	2838	2910	2981	3053	3124	3196	3267
	UCL	2983	3233	3442	3629	3802	3965	4121	4271	4417	4558	4696
	LCL	2122	2015	1949	1905	1875	1854	1841	1834	1831	1833	1838

Satu Model_8	Mare- Forecast	1549	1549	1549	1549	1549	1549	1549	1549	1549	1549	1549	
		UCL	1801	1801	1801	1801	1801	1801	1801	1801	1801	1801	1801
		LCL	1297	1297	1297	1297	1297	1297	1297	1297	1297	1297	1297
Salaj-Model_9	Forecast	1693	1773	1853	1933	2013	2093	2173	2253	2334	2414	2494	
		UCL	2009	2091	2173	2254	2336	2418	2499	2581	2662	2744	2826
		LCL	1377	1455	1534	1612	1691	1769	1848	1926	2005	2083	2162
Centru-Model_10	Forecast	11125	11463	11800	12138	12476	12813	13151	13489	13826	14164	14502	
		UCL	12505	12842	13180	13519	13857	14196	14535	14875	15216	15557	15898
		LCL	9745	10083	10420	10757	11094	11430	11766	12102	12437	12771	13105
Alba-Model_11	Forecast	1700	1762	1825	1888	1951	2014	2077	2139	2202	2265	2328	
		UCL	1977	2040	2103	2166	2229	2291	2354	2417	2480	2543	2606
		LCL	1422	1485	1548	1610	1673	1736	1799	1862	1924	1987	2050
Brasov-Model_12	Forecast	2896	2953	3010	3067	3124	3182	3239	3296	3353	3410	3467	
		UCL	3289	3508	3690	3852	4002	4143	4277	4406	4531	4651	4769
		LCL	2504	2398	2330	2282	2247	2220	2200	2185	2175	2169	2165
Covasna-Model_13	Forecast	802	828	855	881	908	934	960	987	1013	1040	1066	
		UCL	972	1000	1027	1054	1082	1109	1136	1164	1191	1218	1246
		LCL	631	657	682	708	733	759	785	810	836	862	887
Harghita-Model_14	Forecast	1561	1603	1645	1687	1729	1771	1813	1855	1897	1939	1981	
		UCL	1922	1966	2009	2053	2097	2141	2184	2228	2272	2316	2360
		LCL	1199	1240	1280	1320	1360	1401	1441	1481	1521	1562	1602
Mures-Model_15	Forecast	2327	2403	2479	2555	2631	2707	2783	2859	2935	3011	3087	
		UCL	2635	2711	2787	2863	2939	3015	3091	3168	3244	3320	3396
		LCL	2019	2095	2170	2246	2322	2398	2474	2550	2626	2702	2778
Sibiu-Model_16	Forecast	1995	2051	2108	2165	2221	2278	2335	2391	2448	2505	2561	
		UCL	2273	2331	2389	2447	2505	2563	2621	2679	2737	2795	2853
		LCL	1716	1772	1827	1882	1938	1993	2048	2103	2159	2214	2270

Macroregiunea doi-Model_17	Forecast	17091	17661	18231	18801	19371	19941	20511	21081	21651	22221	22790
	UCL	17854	18439	19024	19608	20192	20776	21359	21943	22526	23109	23692
	LCL	16328	16883	17438	17994	18550	19106	19662	20219	20775	21332	21889
Nord-Est-Model_18	Forecast	10193	10588	10983	11379	11774	12169	12564	12960	13355	13750	14145
	UCL	11298	11699	12100	12501	12901	13302	13703	14104	14504	14905	15305
	LCL	9087	9477	9867	10256	10646	11036	11426	11816	12205	12595	12985
Bacau-Model_19	Forecast	1951	2017	2084	2150	2216	2283	2349	2415	2482	2548	2614
	UCL	2153	2220	2288	2355	2423	2490	2558	2625	2693	2760	2827
	LCL	1749	1814	1880	1945	2010	2075	2140	2205	2271	2336	2401
Botosani-Model_20	Forecast	1033	1084	1134	1185	1236	1286	1337	1388	1438	1489	1540
	UCL	1243	1298	1352	1407	1461	1516	1570	1625	1679	1733	1787
	LCL	823	870	916	963	1010	1057	1104	1151	1198	1245	1292
Iasi-Model_21	Forecast	2844	3002	3160	3317	3475	3633	3791	3949	4107	4265	4423
	UCL	3228	3548	3893	4257	4638	5036	5449	5876	6316	6769	7234
	LCL	2460	2455	2426	2378	2313	2231	2134	2022	1898	1761	1611
Neamt-Model_22	Forecast	1684	1743	1802	1861	1920	1979	2038	2097	2156	2215	2274
	UCL	1960	2024	2088	2152	2215	2279	2343	2406	2470	2533	2597
	LCL	1409	1463	1517	1571	1625	1679	1733	1788	1842	1897	1951
Suceava-Model_23	Forecast	2085	2170	2254	2338	2422	2507	2591	2675	2759	2844	2928
	UCL	2300	2385	2471	2556	2641	2726	2812	2897	2982	3068	3153
	LCL	1871	1954	2037	2120	2203	2287	2370	2453	2536	2619	2703
Vaslui-Model_24	Forecast	807	837	868	898	928	959	989	1019	1050	1080	1110
	UCL	899	929	959	990	1020	1050	1081	1111	1141	1172	1202
	LCL	715	746	776	806	837	867	897	928	958	988	1018
Sud-Est-Model_25	Forecast	6728	6728	6728	6728	6728	6728	6728	6728	6728	6728	6728
	UCL	7732	7979	8185	8365	8527	8676	8814	8944	9066	9183	9294
	LCL	5725	5477	5271	5091	4929	4780	4642	4512	4390	4274	4163

Braila-Model_26	Forecast	686	702	717	733	748	763	779	794	809	825	840
	UCL	775	791	807	823	839	855	871	887	903	919	935
	LCL	598	613	627	642	657	672	686	701	716	730	745
Buzau-Model_27	Forecast	961	961	961	961	961	961	961	961	961	961	961
	UCL	1140	1140	1140	1140	1140	1140	1140	1140	1140	1140	1140
	LCL	782	782	782	782	782	782	782	782	782	782	782
Constanta-Model_28	Forecast	2513	2710	2908	3106	3303	3501	3699	3897	4094	4292	4490
	UCL	2868	3212	3639	4124	4654	5220	5819	6447	7102	7784	8489
	LCL	2157	2208	2177	2087	1953	1783	1579	1346	1086	801	491
Galati-Model_29	Forecast	1532	1570	1609	1648	1686	1725	1764	1802	1841	1880	1919
	UCL	1719	1759	1799	1838	1878	1917	1957	1997	2036	2076	2115
	LCL	1344	1382	1419	1457	1495	1533	1570	1608	1646	1684	1722
Tulcea-Model_30	Forecast	363	363	363	363	363	363	363	363	363	363	363
	UCL	417	417	417	417	417	417	417	417	417	417	417
	LCL	309	309	309	309	309	309	309	309	309	309	309
Vrancea-Model_31	Forecast	877	895	913	931	949	967	985	1003	1021	1039	1057
	UCL	997	1015	1033	1051	1069	1087	1105	1123	1141	1159	1177
	LCL	757	775	793	811	829	847	865	883	901	919	937
Macroregiunea trei-Model_32	Forecast	23578	24249	24920	25592	26263	26934	27605	28276	28947	29618	30289
	UCL	24985	26238	27357	28405	29408	30379	31326	32254	33167	34066	34954
	LCL	22172	22260	22484	22778	23118	23488	23884	24298	24728	25170	25624
Sud - Muntenia- Model_33	Forecast	8852	9074	9296	9519	9741	9963	10185	10407	10629	10852	11074
	UCL	9715	9937	10160	10382	10604	10826	11048	11271	11493	11715	11937
	LCL	7989	8211	8433	8655	8877	9100	9322	9544	9766	9988	10210
Arges-Model_34	Forecast	1990	2043	2096	2148	2201	2254	2306	2359	2411	2464	2517
	UCL	2166	2220	2273	2327	2380	2434	2487	2541	2594	2648	2701
	LCL	1814	1866	1918	1970	2021	2073	2125	2177	2229	2280	2332

Calarasi-Model_35	Forecast	667	688	708	728	748	768	788	808	828	848	868
	UCL	744	765	785	806	827	847	868	889	909	930	951
	LCL	591	610	630	649	669	688	707	727	746	766	785
Dâmbovita-Model_36	Forecast	1358	1407	1455	1504	1552	1600	1649	1697	1746	1794	1843
	UCL	1533	1582	1630	1679	1727	1776	1825	1873	1922	1971	2020
	LCL	1183	1231	1280	1328	1377	1425	1473	1521	1570	1618	1666
Giurgiu-Model_37	Forecast	1013	1097	1181	1264	1348	1432	1516	1600	1684	1768	1851
	UCL	1137	1272	1436	1620	1820	2032	2256	2491	2735	2987	3248
	LCL	889	921	925	909	877	832	775	709	633	548	454
Ialomita-Model_38	Forecast	513	524	535	545	556	567	578	589	599	610	621
	UCL	593	604	615	626	636	647	658	669	680	690	701
	LCL	433	443	454	465	476	487	497	508	519	530	541
Prahova-Model_39	Forecast	2806	2842	2878	2914	2950	2985	3021	3057	3093	3129	3165
	UCL	3141	3178	3216	3253	3291	3328	3366	3403	3440	3478	3515
	LCL	2471	2506	2540	2574	2608	2643	2677	2711	2746	2780	2814
Teleorman-Model_40	Forecast	593	613	632	652	671	691	710	730	749	769	788
	UCL	723	796	856	910	960	1007	1052	1095	1137	1177	1217
	LCL	464	430	408	393	382	374	368	364	361	360	359
Bucuresti - Ilfov-Model_41	Forecast	14055	14055	14055	14055	14055	14055	14055	14055	14055	14055	14055
	UCL	15841	16581	17148	17627	18048	18429	18780	19106	19413	19702	19978
	LCL	12269	11529	10962	10483	10062	9681	9330	9004	8697	8408	8132
Bucuresti-Model_42	Forecast	11335	11335	11335	11335	11335	11335	11335	11335	11335	11335	11335
	UCL	12832	13453	13929	14330	14683	15003	15297	15570	15827	16070	16301
	LCL	9838	9217	8741	8340	7987	7667	7373	7100	6843	6600	6369
Ilfov-Model_43	Forecast	2952	3179	3405	3632	3859	4086	4313	4540	4767	4993	5220
	UCL	3199	3643	4126	4642	5189	5763	6363	6986	7632	8300	8988
	LCL	2705	2714	2685	2622	2529	2409	2263	2093	1901	1687	1452

Macroregiunea patru-Model_44	Forecast	13056	13452	13847	14242	14638	15033	15429	15824	16219	16615	17010
	UCL	13565	13970	14375	14779	15184	15588	15993	16397	16801	17205	17608
	LCL	12548	12934	13320	13706	14092	14478	14865	15251	15638	16025	16412
Sud-Vest Oltenia-Model_45	Forecast	5222	5381	5540	5699	5858	6017	6176	6336	6495	6654	6813
	UCL	5734	5896	6057	6219	6380	6542	6703	6865	7026	7188	7349
	LCL	4710	4867	5023	5180	5336	5493	5650	5806	5963	6119	6276
Dolj-Model_46	Forecast	1664	1717	1771	1824	1878	1931	1984	2038	2091	2144	2198
	UCL	1833	1887	1941	1995	2050	2104	2158	2212	2266	2320	2374
	LCL	1495	1548	1600	1653	1706	1758	1811	1863	1916	1968	2021
Gorj-Model_47	Forecast	854	879	904	929	954	979	1005	1030	1055	1080	1105
	UCL	942	967	993	1018	1043	1068	1093	1119	1144	1169	1194
	LCL	765	790	816	841	866	891	916	941	966	991	1016
Mehedinti-Model_48	Forecast	454	466	478	490	502	513	525	537	549	561	573
	UCL	519	558	590	620	647	673	698	721	745	767	789
	LCL	389	374	365	359	356	354	353	353	354	355	357
Olt-Model_49	Forecast	954	983	1013	1042	1071	1101	1130	1159	1189	1218	1248
	UCL	1041	1070	1100	1130	1160	1190	1219	1249	1279	1309	1339
	LCL	867	896	925	954	983	1012	1041	1070	1099	1128	1157
Vâlcea-Model_50	Forecast	1281	1319	1356	1393	1430	1467	1505	1542	1579	1616	1653
	UCL	1509	1550	1591	1633	1674	1715	1756	1797	1838	1879	1920
	LCL	1054	1087	1120	1153	1186	1220	1253	1286	1320	1353	1386
Vest-Model_51	Forecast	7713	7945	8178	8411	8644	8877	9110	9343	9576	9808	10041
	UCL	8614	8847	9079	9312	9545	9778	10011	10244	10477	10710	10943
	LCL	6811	7044	7277	7510	7743	7976	8209	8441	8674	8907	9140
Arad-Model_52	Forecast	2321	2415	2509	2604	2698	2792	2886	2980	3074	3168	3262
	UCL	2699	2795	2891	2987	3083	3179	3275	3371	3467	3563	3659
	LCL	1943	2036	2128	2220	2312	2404	2497	2589	2681	2773	2865

Caras-Severin-Model_53	Forecast	543	543	543	543	543	543	543	543	543	543	543
	UCL	622	622	622	622	622	622	622	622	622	622	622
	LCL	465	465	465	465	465	465	465	465	465	465	465
Hunedoara-Model_54	Forecast	1340	1372	1404	1436	1469	1501	1533	1565	1598	1630	1662
	UCL	1547	1580	1614	1647	1680	1713	1747	1780	1813	1846	1879
	LCL	1132	1164	1195	1226	1257	1288	1320	1351	1382	1413	1445
Timis-Model_55	Forecast	3962	4186	4411	4635	4860	5084	5308	5533	5757	5982	6206
	UCL	4470	4935	5434	5963	6518	7098	7701	8325	8969	9632	10314
	LCL	3454	3438	3388	3308	3201	3070	2916	2741	2546	2331	2098

References

Covaci, B./Suciu, M. C./Covaci, M. (2018): Sectoarele secundar și terțiar, suport al dezvoltării montane în regiunea de Nord-Est a României, in: *Journal of Montanology*, 9, IX, 129-137.

Covaci, M. (2017): Spearman correlations between learning styles from rational level and Gardner intelligence types, in: *Romanian Journal of Psychological Studies*. Hyperion University, 5, 2, 31-38.

Covaci, M. (2019): The Vark Model Investigated at the students from PPPE, in: *Journal of Education Studies (JES)*. Adventus University, 1, 1, 12-19

Covaci, B. (2021), PhD (c) Research report 1, Oradea University

European Commission (2012). Regulation (EU) No 1151/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 November 2012 on quality schemes for agricultural products and foodstuffs. Available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32012R1151>

(Accessed: 14 June 2021)

European Commission, (2014). Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No 665/2014 of 11 March 2014 supplementing Regulation (EU) No 1151/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council with regard to conditions of use of the optional quality term mountain product. Available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32014R0665>

(Accessed: 14 June 2021)

Mountain Perspective Journal (2/2022)

Eurostat, (2020). Business Demography Statistics. Available at <https://goo.gl/fpmXZA> (Accessed: 12 January 2020)

Eurostat, (2020). Regional GDP. Available at <https://goo.gl/EoyR38>. (Accessed: 14 February 2020)

Eurostat (2020). Structural Business Statistics. Available at <https://goo.gl/KMtkVV>. (Accessed: 2 March 2020)

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